

MATHEMATICAL MODELING OF THE MOVEMENT OF SOLID PARTICLES IN CHANNELS AND OPEN BEDS

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Rivers consist of a collection of several tributaries, and these tributaries are formed mainly in mountainous areas. The high speed of the water flow in the rivers, its movement over various rocks that are eroding as a result of a sudden change in natural temperature, causes these rocks to erode and move together. Their sizes are different, and they begin to move by sliding or rolling in the current. During this type of movement, the particles of friction are separated from their composition, and the solid pieces with a sharp appearance begin to turn into rocks with a smooth surface. Based on the results of experimental studies conducted by D.Mind and S.Shubert, it was determined that the speed of the air supplied to the aerodynamic pipe depends on the concentration of soil and nano particles sprinkled on the grids.

Mathematical modeling of particle movement in open channels. To study the movement of particles in channels, we will work on the following problem. A view of the channel is depicted in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. Account channel view

A channel with water height $H=3.6$ meters and channel length $L=100H=360$ meters was obtained. Here, the speed of water was taken as $U=0.35, 0.55, 0.75, 1$ m/s, and the movement of particles with a diameter of $D=0.05$ to 1 mm was studied.

RANS based on the Nave-Stokes equation and Spalart-Allmares differential equations of turbulence have the following form in the Cartesian coordinate

$$\text{system [2].} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{\partial U}{\partial t} + U \frac{\partial U}{\partial x} + V \frac{\partial U}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left((v + \tilde{v}) \frac{\partial U}{\partial y} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left((v + \tilde{v}) \frac{\partial U}{\partial x} \right) + K(U - U_p), \\ \frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + U \frac{\partial V}{\partial x} + V \frac{\partial V}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial p}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left((v + \tilde{v}) \frac{\partial V}{\partial y} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left((v + \tilde{v}) \frac{\partial V}{\partial x} \right) - g + K(V - V_p), \\ \frac{\partial \tilde{v}}{\partial t} + U \frac{\partial \tilde{v}}{\partial x} + V \frac{\partial \tilde{v}}{\partial y} = C_{b1} (1 - f_{t2}) \tilde{S} \tilde{v} - \left[C_{w1} f_w - \frac{C_{b1}}{k^2} f_{t2} \right] \left(\frac{\tilde{v}}{d} \right)^2 + \\ + \frac{1}{\sigma} \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left((v + \tilde{v}) \frac{\partial \tilde{v}}{\partial y} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left((v + \tilde{v}) \frac{\partial \tilde{v}}{\partial x} \right) \right] + \frac{C_{b2}}{\sigma} \left(\left(\frac{\partial \tilde{v}}{\partial x} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial \tilde{v}}{\partial y} \right)^2 \right) \\ \frac{dU_p}{dt} = K(U - U_p), \quad \frac{dV_p}{dt} = K(V - V_p) - g. \end{array} \right. \quad (1)$$

Here - longitudinal and transverse speed of water in the channel. U_p, V_p - particle velocities. We use the following equation to relate the turbulent viscosity: $\nu_t = \tilde{v} f_{v1}$

Additional functions of the Spalart-Allmares model are defined as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} f_{v1} &= \frac{x^3}{x^3 + c_{v1}^3}, \quad x = \frac{\tilde{v}}{v}, \quad \tilde{S} = \Omega + \frac{\tilde{v}}{k^2 d^2} f_{v2}. \\ f_w &= g \left[\frac{1 + C_{w3}^6}{g^6 + C_{w3}^6} \right], \quad g = r + C_{w2} (r^6 - r), \quad f_{v2} = 1 - \frac{x}{1 + x f_{v1}}, \quad g = r + c_{w2} (r^6 - r), \quad (2) \\ f_{t2} &= c_{t3} \exp(-c_{t4} x^2), \quad r = \min \left[\frac{\tilde{v}}{\tilde{S} k^2 d^2}, 10 \right], \quad W_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial U_i}{\partial x_j} - \frac{\partial U_j}{\partial x_i} \right). \end{aligned}$$

The phase interaction coefficient in turbulent motion is determined as follows.

$$K = \frac{18 \rho \nu}{\rho_p \delta^2} \quad (2)$$

Here ρ_p - solid particle density, ρ - water density, δ - particle diameter.

$$Re_d = \frac{g \cdot d}{\nu} \quad \text{- Reynolds number for the particle, } \nu \text{ - kinematic viscosity}$$

Let's make equation 1 dimensionless, that is, all velocities are relative to the velocity at the entrance to the channel, and dimensions are relative to the height

of the water. In the dimensionless case, equation 1 looks like this

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} \frac{\partial U}{\partial t} + U \frac{\partial U}{\partial x} + V \frac{\partial U}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left((v + \tilde{v}) \frac{\partial U}{\partial y} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left((v + \tilde{v}) \frac{\partial U}{\partial x} \right) + K(U - U_p), \\ \frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + U \frac{\partial V}{\partial x} + V \frac{\partial V}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial p}{\partial y} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left((v + \tilde{v}) \frac{\partial V}{\partial y} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left((v + \tilde{v}) \frac{\partial V}{\partial x} \right) - g + K(V - V_p), \\ \frac{\partial \tilde{v}}{\partial t} + U \frac{\partial \tilde{v}}{\partial x} + V \frac{\partial \tilde{v}}{\partial y} &= C_{b1}(1 - f_{t2}) \tilde{S}\tilde{v} - \left[C_{w1} f_w - \frac{C_{b1}}{k^2} f_{t2} \right] \left(\frac{\tilde{v}}{d} \right)^2 + \\ &+ \frac{1}{\sigma} \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left((v + \tilde{v}) \frac{\partial \tilde{v}}{\partial y} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left((v + \tilde{v}) \frac{\partial \tilde{v}}{\partial x} \right) \right] + \frac{C_{b2}}{\sigma} \left[\left(\frac{\partial \tilde{v}}{\partial x} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial \tilde{v}}{\partial y} \right)^2 \right] \\ \frac{dU_p}{dt} &= K(U - U_p), \quad \frac{dV_p}{dt} = K(V - V_p) - g. \end{aligned} \right. \quad (4)$$

Initial and boundary conditions

Entering

$$U = U_p = \int_{j=1}^n e^{(0.05 \ln(\frac{j}{n}))}, \quad V = V_p = 0.$$

An extrapolation condition was used for all velocities in the output.

$$\frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial x^2} = \frac{\partial^2 U_p}{\partial x^2} = \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial x^2} = \frac{\partial^2 V_p}{\partial x^2} = \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial x^2} = 0.$$

An extrapolation condition was used for all velocities in the output.

$$U = U_p = V = V_p = 0.$$

Analysis of numerical results

The figure below shows the graphs of the transverse and longitudinal velocities of the flow in different sections of the channel.

Figure 2. Transverse speed of flow in different sections of the channel

The figure below shows a graph of particle settling distance as a function of flow velocity.

Figure 3. The distance that particles settle depending on the speed of the flow is the speed of the flow

[3] a) $U=0.35$ m/s, b) $U=0.55$ m/s, c) $U=0.75$ m/s, d) $U=1$ m/s.

In this article, the movement of solid particles in open channels was studied. The RANS method and the Spalart-Allmares turbulence model were used to determine the flow velocities. A Lagrangian approach was used to determine the trajectory of the particles. In numerical calculations, it was determined that if the size and size of the particle is large, it will sink very quickly, if the particle is light, it will travel a long distance, and it is shown in the graphs.

References a:

1. Umarbekovna D. D. ISSUES OF PRODUCT EXPORT OF SMALL BUSINESS AND ENTREPRENEURIAL ENTITIES //World Economics and Finance Bulletin. – 2022. – T. 13. – C. 57-58.
2. Utanov B. Q., Maxamadrahimov M. O. BUILDING CORPORATION MANAGEMENT: IN CASE OF THE USA AND JAPAN MODELS //INSTITUTIONAL

FRAMEWORK OF THE ECONOMY FUNCTIONING IN CONDITIONS OF TRANSFORMATION. – 2014. – С. 304-306.

3. Утанов Б. К. ЭКОНОМЕТРИЧЕСКОЕ МОДЕЛИРОВАНИЕ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ МНОГОПРОФИЛЬНЫХ ФЕРМЕРСЬКИХ ХОЗЯЙСТВ //К64 Конкурентоспроможна модель інноваційного розвитку економіки України: матеріали III Міжнар. наук.-практ. конф., м. Кропивницький, 14 квіт. 2020 р./М-во освіти і науки України, Центральноукраїн. нац. техн. ун-т.—Кропивницький: ЦНТУ, 2020.—358 с. – 2020. – С. 344.

4. Khabibullayev I., Utanov B. K. STATISTICAL INDICATORS OF FISCAL SYSTEMS AND METHODS OF ACCOUNTING //Economics & Law. – 2015. – Т. 51. – №. 5.

5. Absalamova G. S. VIEWS OF FRENCH RENAISSANCE THINKERS ON CHILD UPBRINGING //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. Special Issue 1. – С. 12-17.

6. Absalamova G. FRANSUZ MUTAFAKKIRI MICHEL DE MONTEN FARZAND TARBIYASI XUSUSIDA: FRANSUZ MUTAFAKKIRI MICHEL DE MONTEN FARZAND TARBIYASI XUSUSIDA //Журнал иностранных языков и лингвистики. – 2021. – Т. 4. – №. 9.

7. Beknazarova M., Saypiyev T. NAKARBOKSIMETILTSELLYULOZANI GETEROGEN SHAROITDA PARCHALASH VA GETEROGEN KATALIZ, GETEROGEN TIZIM: XUSUSIYATLARI, TASNIFI VA USULLARI //Academic research in modern science. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 12. – С. 45-53.

8. Sharifovna A. G. Michel Monten's Style in His “Essays” //Procedia of Social Sciences and Humanities. – 2021. – Т. 1. – С. 364-368.

9. Жанонова С. Б. Этимология Названия Растений //Periodica Journal of Modern Philosophy, Social Sciences and Humanities. – 2022. – Т. 6. – С. 113-116.

10. Janonova S. B. Place and application of terminology in agriculture //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2021. – Т. 11. – №. 7. – С. 255-258.

11. Bazarov D.R. Arifjonov A.M. va boshqalar “O’zandagi jarayonlar gidravlikasi”. Toshkent 2019.

12. Loitsyansky L.G. The mechanics of fluid and gas, Moscow, Science. p. 840, Механика жидкости и газа, Moscow, Nauka, (1987)

13. Андерсон Д., Таннехил Дюю., Плетчер Р. Вычислительная гидромеханика и теплообмен //- М.: Мир, 1990.- Т.1- 384с.; Т.2 - 392с

14. Patankar S.V. Numerical Heat Transfer and Fluid Flow. Taylor&Francis. ISBN 978-0-89116-522-4, 1980.
15. Spalart P.R., Shur M.L. On the sensitization of turbulence models to rotational and curvature // Aerospace Science and Technology. 1997. Vol. 1, No. 5. 297-302.
16. Самарский А. А., Николаев Е.С. Методы решения сеточных уравнений. М.: Наука, 1978. – 592 с.
17. Kolmogorov A.N. Equations of turbulent motion of an incompressible fluid. Izvestia Academy of Sciences, USSR; 1942, Physics 6: – P. 56-58.
18. Наврузов, Дилшод Примкулович, and Сардор Кахарбоевич Абдухамидов. "ДВУХШАГОВАЯ НЕЯВНАЯ СХЕМА ПИСМЕНА-РИКФОРДА ДЛЯ РЕШЕНИЯ УРАВНЕНИЕ ЛАПЛАСА." INNOVATION IN THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM 2.18 (2022): 803-808.
19. Abduxamidov S. K., Omonov Z. J., Chorshanbiyeva L. T. ISSUES OF CALCULATING THE TRANSVERSE FORCE AND BENDING MOMENTS FOR VARIOUS TYPES OF FENCES IMPOSED BY EXTERNAL FORCES //Archive of Conferences. – 2021. – С. 63-66.

